

**GENDER CONSCIOUSNESS IN IFA DIVINATION POETRY
OR
[IFA DIVINATION POETRY AND THE CONSTRUCTION OF
GENDER]**

By

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Abstract

Gender consciousness is a phrase that has come to dominate gender studies discourse in recent times, and it is used interchangeably with gender awareness and self-awareness; it is considered as a precondition for feminism. However, research in gender consciousness is geared towards mainstream sociology and written literature to the neglect of oral literature and Ifa divination poetry in particular. This study is therefore designed to examine gender consciousness in Ifa divination poetry by exploring the issue of gender consciousness in Ifa divination poetry. By so doing, the study reveals that Ifa divination poetry plays a significant role in designating gender. The paper reveals further that women are assigned gender roles because society is dominated by patriarchy, does not want women to grow beyond their assigned position so that they may remain subjugated economically. The reason women are at the lower rung of the economic and social ladders is because of the gender roles they are assigned, even though they work so hard and contribute to global economy, yet they constitute the highest index of poverty rate. Under the guise of admiration, Ifa divination poetry declasses women and make them subservient to patriarchy. The paper also reveals that gender roles and gender markers change with time and that gender schema and sexual dimorphism are not static, although these markers may be peculiar to one gender, their distinction is not always clear-cut.

Keywords: Gender consciousness, Ifa divination poetry, Roles, Patriarchy

Introduction

In recent times, the term gender consciousness” has pervaded many gender-based discourses (Brody and Celeste 2008; Bierema 2003; Sowards et al 2004; Prindeville et al 2007; Herring and Marken 2008), and has often been used interchangeably with gender awareness and self-awareness. Gender awareness and feminism are related, and many scholars have approached gender awareness discourse from a feminist perspective. To avoid misunderstanding, Hogeland (1994:19), contrasts the two terms thus:

Gender consciousness is a necessary precondition for feminist consciousness, but they are not the same. The difference lies in the link between gender and politics. Feminism politicizes gender consciousness, inserts it into a systematic analysis of histories and structures of domination and privilege.

Elsewhere, Patricia Gurin (1985) defines feminism as politicized gender consciousness. Based on the foregoing, therefore, gender consciousness is a step towards feminism.

According to Herring and Marken (2008:1), “gender consciousness is the recognition that one’s physical sex shapes one’s relationship to the political world. Similar to other forms of group consciousness, it entails identification with others like oneself, a positive toward them, and a sense of connectedness with the group and its wellbeing”. There are three stages in gender consciousness development and according to Carrol (1989:328) they are:

First, the individual begins to identify with women, acknowledging common interests. Second, s/he notices disparities in how women are treated and feels this is unjust. Third, s/he recognizes that the problems women face demand collective, political, solutions and cannot be solved through individual effort.

The whole system of gender consciousness is characterized by (a) a sense of interdependence and shared fate with other women, (b) recognition of women's relatively low status and power compared to men, (c) attribution of power differentials to illegitimate sources, such as institutionalized sexism, and (d) an orientation toward collective action to improve women's position in society (S. Herring and J. Marken, 2008: p.1).

Over the years, gender consciousness has been seen to have many advantages. Gender consciousness now plays a crucial role in leading women to take political

action, resonating Tolleson Rinehart's (1992:139) submission that gender consciousness plays important role propelling women to political action to redress their social conditions. Rinehart says,

If women require special resources to overcome the lack of welcome they may find as they try to become political, gender consciousness can provide them. Gender identification and gender role ideology furnish these means by providing an intrinsic belief system: I can and should participate; and a sense of extrinsic support: I do this with and for others like me.

However fortuitous gender consciousness may be, the circumstances that gave rise to the concept must not be forgotten. Gender consciousness arises from the gender identity given to males and females in any given society as a result of biological configuration. Biological and physical conditions such as hormones, chromosomes, internal and external genitals and other features determine the sex of male and female. Based on the cultural perception of male and female characteristics roles are given accordingly, which now become the individual gender. It is on this ground Olajubu (2014), defines gender as capacities and attributes assigned to a person based on their alleged sexual characteristics. She further argues that gender is constructed within a people's living experience, embedded in the base of their philosophy and manifested at the theoretical and pragmatic level of their policy.

Gender roles are learned and transmitted through acculturation and socialization. In many cultures, boys and girls have different kinds of acts they are allowed to participate in, specific to their sex- for boys, acts that will make them develop male traits; for girls, acts that will make them develop female traits. For instance, boys are given toy guns to play with while girls are given dolls to play. This distinction also influences punishment given to them; influences their career choices and their view of themselves in relation to others; peers, parents, teachers, culture, society and the social media reinforce their masculine or feminine view of themselves.

In all societies, there are parameters for determining gender of which the first is sex; however, beyond sex, no two cultures have the same view about gender. For instance, many cultures of the world, a child is considered as the sole property of the father, unlike other parts of the world. Oakley (1972:128) has the below to say about the Arapesh and the Trobriand Islanders.

The Arapesh, for example, consider that the business of bearing and rearing a child belongs to father and mother equally, and equally disqualifies them for other roles. Men as well as women 'make' and 'have'

babies, and the verb 'to bear a child' is used indiscriminately of either a man or a woman. Child-bearing is believed to be as debilitating for the man as it is for the woman. The father goes to bed and is described as 'having a baby' when the child is born.... The Trobriand Islanders are renowned for their ignorance of the father's biological role in reproduction, but they stress the need for the father to share with the mother all tasks involved in bringing up children.

Understanding this cultural difference concerning gender is imperative to the understanding of developmental processes of girls and boys, women and men, in their own ranks. Sex is an accident of human biology; humans are born female and male; men impregnate; women conceive, deliver and breastfeed. It on these accidental biological differences, attitudes, behaviours, traits, and roles that gender roles are configured. These roles are the basis of human societies and the foundation on which they are laid; any attempt at overturning, questioning or subverting them may be considered treasonous and a threat to the human population. Nevertheless, it is sacrosanct to learn how we become who we are, as boys and girls, men and women, masculine and feminine; why a particular gender is more educated than the other and the attendant relative poverty and wealth. It is important to note that “what we learn depends on the society into which we are born, and our position within it, our relative poverty or wealth, and our ethnic group for unlike sex, gender roles are variable” (*The Oxfam Gender Training Manual*, p.100).

In some cultures of the world, women are professionals, leaders, and own properties, among others; in other cultures, it is a taboo. However, when unforeseen occurrences occur, such as natural disasters, war, famine, some of those stringent cultures become relaxed and make room for women to grow. What this means is that gender role is not static; as societies change, so with gender roles. Gender consciousness looks at these dynamics, “it asks not only who does what, but also who makes the decisions, and who derives the benefit, who uses resources such as land, or credit, and who controls these resources; and what other factors influence relationships, such as laws about property rights and inheritance” (*The Oxfam Gender Training Manual*, p. 101). Gender consciousness highlights the fact that due to gender, men and women have different experiences, which shape their outlook on life and their selves in relation to others, their environment, and the social spheres, of which, consequences may include self-effacing attitude, in extreme cases gender shame and repression, a consciousness systemic gender fostered.

All cultures have their methods of propagating and fostering gender. Ifa divination plays a major role in the Yoruba society as Ifa has all answers for all the issues in the world including Gender issues. The Ifa divination poetry covers the Yoruba cosmic belief system, which includes Yoruba people's beliefs about gender roles, gender representation, gender stereotypes, and even gender Shame. Gender Shame for this research stands for instances when people are ashamed, shamed, and feel less confident of their gender and wish to have been born of another sex because of how society receives that particular gender and because of the gender stereotypes attached to that gender. These shape the way society receives a particular gender as well as how various genders are viewed. The Ifa corpus is one of the most studied traditional corpora in the world. According to Olatunji (2013), Ifa corpus is a compendium of wisdom, religion, morality, and culture, and the Yoruba people regard it as the source of intellectual development. By morality, it denotes that, through Ifa corpus, attitudes and roles are assigned and regulated; what this means is that gender roles in Yoruba may be attributed to Ifa.

Yoruba is an ethnic group in Western Nigeria with a significant population of about 35 million people. In addition to Nigeria, Yoruba people are in Benin, Togo, Ghana, Sierra Leone, and Ivory Coast. There is also the Yoruba diaspora; those dispersed by the transatlantic slave trade to the Latin Americas such as the Caribbean Islands and Brazil; those who were in the 1960s and 1980s dispersed economically and politically to the United Kingdom, United States, among others. A significant thing to note about the Yoruba in the Western Hemisphere is that, however displaced they are, kept a significant proportion of their culture with them, and still practice it till date. Maureen Warner-Lewis and other like-minded people have written a number of scholarly articles on the Yoruba culture in the Caribbean Island and Brazil.

The Yoruba people, like all other ethnic nationalities in West Africa, has been impacted seriously by colonialism and cultural imperialism both from European hegemony and Islamist Jihadist; so that, one now finds multiculturalism in Yoruba, of those who are Christians, Muslims, and traditional worshipers. Even among the so-called professed Muslim and Christians, there some who unknowingly and knowingly still hold up to the principles of the original traditional faith of the departed holy ancestors. The Yoruba culture, heavily impacted as it may, a way of life still remains, and is being taught in schools, universities; it is gathering influences around the world as it is being promoted by cultural activists and academic intellectuals such as Wole Soyinka and Toyin Falola, and the social media. Much of Yoruba has been spread out into the world inhabiting both physical and mental spaces, of which Yoruba religion is one.

The Yoruba religion comprises the Yoruba worldview and spiritual concepts of the Yoruba people. According to Kola Abimbola (2005), Yoruba religion is derived from diverse traditions and has no sole founder; the belief systems are part of Ifa,

which is the combination of songs, stories, histories, and concepts that constitute the Yoruba community and worldview. The Yoruba, like every other ethnic nationality on the surface of the earth, have their own view of the world – the universe, ranging from birth to death, which is the circle of life; the myth of creation. For instance, the Yoruba believe that Ile-Ife is the centre of the world, and all other races started from there. The Yoruba believe that human nature is dualistic; when an individual dies, he joins his ancestors. As such, death is viewed not as an end to life, but a means to another life – death is a transition. The death of the body does not mean the death of the soul. Therefore, to the Yoruba, the body is liable to perish but the soul is not, is indivisible and much more powerful, and can be reborn in the human world. The Yoruba name, “Baba,” stems from the belief that a member of a deceased family who died has been reborn; as such, he is accorded similar respect as when he was alive. The dual nature of man also involves the question of morality – as body and spirit is in one body, so is both good and evil. To the Yoruba, the question of evil is straddled and sometimes viewed as an assignment to be performed, not necessarily and entirely the machinations of the actor. The gods must have destined the actor - that is, the person, whom evil is attributed to. Therefore, the evil man is merely a vehicle to realize a predestined course.

Another aspect of the Yoruba worldview is the Orisa *Orisa* is one of the most famous concepts in the Yoruba worldview, and it does not, according to Soyinka (1999:85) “permit in tenet, liturgy, catechism or practice, that pernicious dictum: I believe, therefore, I am... Orunmila does not permit it. Obatala cannot conceive it. Ogun will take up arms against it. Not one of the Odu of Ifa suggests it.”

Within the Yoruba pantheon, Orunmila is the god of wisdom, and Esu, the co-guardian of the crossroads with Orunmila, is the sole messenger of the gods. Esu conveys messages from the gods to mortals, and he conveys them depending on the manner in which he is received- simply or esoterically, making them prone to misinterpretation; it is on this ground he is regarded as leader, teacher, trickster, a jester, and cunning or deceitful, denoting his dual nature. Orunmila is the god of wisdom and intellectual development. Orunmila is also the god of the past, present, and future; he influences and reveals the past, present, and future through Ifa divination.

Ifa divination is communication between God and men (Bascom 1969). Ifa corpus is a special system, which, according to the Yoruba people, has answers to everything in human life. The Ifa divination is the most important part of the Ifa system, and it has hidden codes, which only the Babalawo, the Ifa priest, can decipher, using sacred palm-nuts and a chain. The *Ese-Ifa* is considered the most important part of Ifa divination; it is poetically recited by the priest in poetic form, repeatedly conducting incantations. The Ifa poetic renditions are considered by scholars to be as old as the nation (Bascom 1969; Abimbola, 1976,1977; Abimbola

2005; Jegede 2010). These oracular chants are referred to as Ifa divination poetry and literary corpus (Abimbola 1977).

The Ifa divination system utilizes an extensive text and mathematical formulas. The Ifa literary corpus, called Odu, consists of 256 parts subdivided into verses called Ese, whose exact number is unknown as they are constantly increasing (there are about 800 ese per Odu). Each of the 256 Odu has its specific language. The Ese reflect Yoruba history, language, beliefs, cosmology, vision and contemporary social issues, a knowledge preserved by the Ifa priest and transmitted within Yoruba communities and to Ifa apprentices. Unlike other forms of divination in the region that employ spirit mediums, Ifa divination does not rely on oracular powers but rather on a system of signs that are interpreted by a diviner, the Ifa priest or Babalawo, literally “the priest’s father,” who is sought after whenever an important individual or collective decision is to be made. In addition, people consult the Babalawo for solutions to whatever afflictions they have, to know the fate of a child, marriage, and the outcome of whatever venture they want to pursue, and to avert an impending danger. The corpus also consists of beliefs, narratives, warnings, gender roles, gender representation, gender stereotypes, and gender Shame. People look to Ifa poetry for the gender roles assigned to them, for them to be conscious of their gender. Thus, through Ifa mechanism, people get to learn about their gender and are socialized accordingly. It is this perception of Ifa as a gender designator that informs this research, and it is designed to highlight gender consciousness as reflected in the Ifa divination poetry.

Literature and the African Female Gender

Literature is a mirror of society, and it has been used to further the course of people over time. Among the first generation of African writers, literature was used to further the course of men to the neglect of women. In one way or another, women are misrepresented in their works: as weaker vessels, unthinking and helpless beings. In Joyce Carry’s *Mister Johnson* (1939), the African woman is portrayed as unthinking being thus:

...is following Johnson out of the hut when he puts his hand through her arm, clasps her hand and conducts her through the crowd outside. Bamu does not like this. She wants to walk behind her husband, but she allows herself to be pulled along (41).

From the above quotation, the African woman is seen walking behind her husband, dragged along without having a say. On the other hand, Matumbi, Sergeant Gollup’s mistress is depicted as an easy target, someone who could be violently attacked anytime in a drunken bolt. This is narrated thus:

... he uses only his feet and fists... on Sunday... he will sometimes thrash Matumbi with a stick, flog her or even batter her with a chair until she lies on the floor covered with blood... in fact, she suffered no more, in four years of Sundays, than a broken arm, a split ear, and a few deep scars... She is boundless greedy and lazy; she will not even scratch herself if she can get the small boy to do it. Her virtue is good humour. She will sit for hours apparently thinking of nothing (25-126).

The last sentence in the quote reinforces the idea that women are unthinking beings, and this classification resonates in societies and in literature. *Things Fall Apart* (1958), written by Chinua Achebe, and which inaugurated African literature also does not speak well of women; it follows the model set by European writers as found in *Mister Johnson*. While commenting on *Things Fall Apart*, Uko (2006) states that

Achebe's *Things Fall Apart*, consciously recreated the authentic Africa, African landscape and African humanity, in its portrayal of men of valor and honor- Okonkwo, Obierika, Ezeulo, Uchendu, and others. The obvious omission is in *Things Fall Apart* not consciously recreating a credible African woman who knows her own mind and even while married and performing her nurturing roles has her ambitions and contributes to the dynamics of economics in the micro and macro systems.

The failure on the part of African male writers to represent the African woman as she really is in literature, prompted female writers to engage the art of literature to rewrite the story of women, an art that is now regarded as feminist ethos or feminism- the quest for females to free themselves from the patriarchal clutches and mega or grand narratives of oppression, cultural and economic inferiorization and marginalization promoted by men, subverting male dominance, to engender in equality among the genders. The process of rewriting and freeing women from every sort of oppression and victimization, which is the thrust of this research, a feminist imperative produced in Africa, renowned female writers such as Zulu Sofola, Efua Sutherland, Zenab Alkali, Tess Nweme, Chimmamanda Ngozi Adichie, among others. Their mission is to rewrite the African woman's story and give her a new status deserving of her role in human and community development, contrary to the male writers' depiction of women. The first few writers who engaged in this feminist consciousness in African literature are regarded as literary

foremothers. Their works paved the way for more female writers to walk the literary landscape of Africa, and partake in the campaign against women's oppression and subjugation. According to Uko (85), "there is no disputing the fact that the pioneering feat of Flora Nwapa through the publication of *Efuru* in 1966 shook the women from slumber and melancholic acquiescence to female stereotypes, gender discrimination and female invisibility". The feminist imperative is seen in their works in the manner they write back to their male counterparts through the characterization of male stereotypes much the same way the male writers did to female characters in their works. Taiwo, cited in Chukwuma (1989:10)

The novelist has done what she knows best how to do. She has created a world of women where for the most part, attempts to portray male characters in unfavourable light may be an intentional device to take it back on men because of their image in the novels written by men.

It is important to note that feminism is a foreign ideology and when it gained entrance into African literature it assumed a different stance contrary to the one practiced in Europe and America; it is for this reason feminism has remained as it came in the first place, it was not popular. Obafemi (1994:85) contends that

...feminism as an active ideological preoccupation does not really exist concretely in Nigeria, the way it was in Europe and America. Apart from women in Nigeria, a fledging feminist organization yet to implant its relevance on the social consciousness of Nigerian people, the only remarkable women's organization to whom most of the initiative of popular mobilization belongs is the largely body called the national Council of Nigerian Women.

Obafemi's contention here is that feminism has not gained solid ground in Nigeria, but this does not mean Africa is not a "fertile terrain pre-occupied with dramatic cultural workers" (Obafemi 1994: p. 84).

Since the appearance of Flora Nwapa on the literary landscape of Africa, women have occupied notable positions in the literary scene. Charles Nnolim (2006:31) says that "after Cyprian Ekwensi, the field of literature for children and also adolescent seems to have become dominated by our female writers". And Mojola (1989:37) while discussing novels of Adaora Ulasi states that "female writers have blazed the trail in every literary genre and sub-genre practiced so far in Nigeria except one: the detective novel written in English," attesting to the fact that women condition has changed overtime, thanks to gender consciousness.

Gender Designation and Occupational Discrimination in Ifa Divination Poetry

All cultures have their methods of propagating and fostering gender. Ifa divination plays a major role in the Yoruba society as Ifa has all answers for all the issues in the world including Gender issues. The Ifa divination poetry covers the Yoruba cosmic belief system, which includes Yoruba people's belief about gender roles, gender representation, gender stereotypes even gender shame. By gender shame, it means when people are ashamed, shamed, and feels less confident of their gender and wish to have been born of another sex because of how the society receives a particular gender and because of the gender stereotypes attached to that gender.

The Ifa divination poetry has a lot to say about gender roles and attaches various stereotypes to various genders. Gender roles are roles that men and women are expected to occupy based on their sex. These roles are based on the different expectations, that individuals, groups and societies have of people based on their sex and based on each society's values and belief about gender, while gender stereotypes are values that are attached to a particular gender. The concept of gender roles contribute to patriarchy is examined in the following Odu-Ifa, *Ese Ifa Okanran-Meji* and *Iwori Igosunis*.

"Odu Ifa Okanran –Meji" is one of the many Ifa divination poems that highlight gender roles in the Yoruba cosmology. The poem is about Onigoosun's wife who pounds camwood. Camwood is one of many African hardwood trees, and camwood is essentially known for active ingredients that are harnessed to protect the human skin. Medically, camwood naturally contains antioxidant properties that help in regulating blood circulation to the skin area and removes toxic material from the skin layers. It also protects the skin from wrinkling; giving the skin the firmness it needs while improving the skin's elasticity. As such, when the poet says "The Iwori that pounds camwood", it reveals to the reader that Iwori whom the poet talks about utilises active ingredients of camwood to treat skin infections. However, it is not the medical profession that the poet intends to portray since he says in the second line that "The one that makes pap paste, the wife of Onigoosun". It seems that the poet draws attention to the fact that Onigoosun marries many wives of which one is Iwori and, the poet distinguishes Iwori from the other wives by what Iwori does, specifically her profession – she pounds camwood to treat skin infections and makes pap. Furthermore, Iwori is also identified by her marriage to her husband thus: "She married a husband from the ruler's lineage".

The implication of professional role and marital status of Iwori is that they define Iwori's relationship with others, her roles become her point of reference and identities, and most importantly, situate her as an appendage to others especially her husband; she is not only recognised as the women who makes pap, pounds camwood but also the woman who married a husband from the ruler's lineage.

Worthy of note in addition to the identifiers, is the profession type: skincare work and pap making. It seems from inception that these professions were in the domain of the female gender since it is attributed to Iwori, and this is corroborated by the below poet's statement

She produced pap paste and became prosperous
Her husband saw that she is becoming prosperous
He started selling pap paste like his wife
However, he failed to prosper in the trade like his wife
He went for divination after several failures
He was told the work is not for him
Because it is the work of a woman.
Oun gun ogi o si n rise
Oko ko ri oju gogi gogi mo
Nitori o ti lowo lowo
Oko re ba bere si gun ogi bi ti iyawo
Pe ki oun naa o le lowo
Sugbon ko ri se
Igba to pe, o di fa

Bem (1983 and 1993) contends in his theory of gender socialization that cultures reinforce gender and enable people to make sense of their own experience of the environment and process information in relation to their perception of what they see. It is as Bem (1993:154) contends, "Through this process people acquire traits and personalities that are consistent with their understandings of themselves as male or female. They develop gender schemas; cognitive structures (or lenses) that help people assimilate and organize perception". Bem goes further to aver that "the gendered personality is more than a particular collection of masculine or feminine traits; it is also a way of looking at reality that produces and reproduces those traits during a lifetime of self-construction", whereby by the larger world populated by gendered people is that source of "raw material" through which gender identities are configured (Bem 1993: p.154). Gender schema works within the frame of acceptability whereby the belief that what is acceptable for females is not acceptable or appropriate for males (and vice versa) and that anyone who deviates from these standards of appropriate femaleness and maleness is unnatural or immoral. It is these notions that become part of people's internalized gender

schemas, thus leading them to think of the other gender as the opposite sex. This schema also affects their choice of profession leading them to regard certain types of jobs as female or male.

This is what we find in the above Odu-Ifa. Due to the fact that gender schema erects the frame of acceptability, so that, what is acceptable to female is not acceptable to males inhibits Iwori's husband's success at making pap. As a result, he consults a diviner who reveals to him that the trade is not for men but for women.

He went for divination after several failures

He was told the work is not for him

Because it is the work of a woman.

Igba to pe, o di fa

Won ni a o fi ise ton se ran an

Nitori owo obinrin ni

His failure is not because of he could not make the pap as good as the wife, but rather, it is because of the personality and the reality that produce and reproduce those traits during a lifetime of self-construction – it is has been self-constructed overtime that pap making is for women alone, and the society frowns against the husband's hijacking of the business hence his failure. However, being a product of sexual dimorphism, that is configuration and schematised process of production and reproduction, Iwori's succeeds at that business, and the poet says,

She produced pap paste and became prosperous

Her husband saw that she is becoming prosperous

He started selling pap paste like his wife

Oun gun ogi o si n rise

Okoko ri oju gogi gogi mo

Nitori o ti lowo lowo

In African societies, is a practice or common belief that certain professions are for either females or males: Hair cutting, hunting, mechanical repairs, mason (bricklayer), among others, are for men whereas restaurants, hair stylist, Nanny, hawking, among others, are for women; a bridge is often considered as anomaly and it is this notion that gradually becomes part of people's internalized gender schemas, thus leading them to think of the other gender profession as the opposite and exclusively gendered. Among the Yoruba people, the belief that women are better in the kitchen, with menial jobs and selling of wares is prominent, and these

are the kind of jobs women participate in. Women have been stereotyped to be market people and this explains why we have the Phrase “*Iyaloja*” which means market woman and we hardly hear the phrase “*baba oloja*” (market men) and also the reason we have associations like Market Women Association. The gender stereotype that there are women’s profession and there are men’s profession; one will not be successful if one goes outside one’s gender’s profession. It is demeaning for a man to get himself engaged in jobs that are for women and it is over ambitious for a woman to also get herself involved in a man’s job. For example, it is needless in a traditional Yoruba society to have a man as a hawker, a cook and as a nanny because they are considered women’s affair. While a woman who is a hunter or a warrior is not considered a woman but a man even though she is a woman.

Another aspect of the poem worthy of note is Iwori husband’s hijack of the pap making business. The poets says that the moment “Her husband saw that she is becoming prosperous/ He started selling pap paste like his wife”. It can be argued that the reason pap making business was considered women’s job is because of low-income rate; for this reason, men designated it for women since the proceeds of pap making cannot elevate the status of women to enable them seek for economic and political powers. As such, the moment the husband notices the wife’s success in the pap paste business he decides to come into it because he now sees powers in it. Therefore, if society had known from the beginning that pap paste business is lucrative, they would not have assigned it to women so as to further entrench the patriarchal agenda.

In addition to gender schema, the reason Onigoosun fails to succeed could be attributed to gender stereotype. Owing to the fact that women have been assigned to do certain jobs such as cooking, that is, kitchen jobs, they know more about kitchen activities far more than men do and that may have contributed to Iwor’s success. But since men have been configured and shielded from kitchen activities, viewing them as women’s job, make them to not know much about cooking activities and may have manifested in the pap paste Onigoosun makes hence his failure. If there were no distinctions as to who will work in the kitchen the story could have been better.

The above Ifa divination poetry shows the phallocentric belief of the Yoruba society about gender less stressful economic activity belongs to the women folks. The last line of the poem points to occupations like Pap paste making which is a menial occupation as being for women and not for men. The man was expected to engage in occupations like farming, hunting, etc. One striking thing about the poem is the way Ifa blames the man’s gender for his failure in the choice of occupation. His incompetence, lack of experience or selfish reasons for taking up the job was not considered by the oracle but his gender was the only thing the oracle picked as being responsible for his failure. It is obvious that gender has nothing to do with

the man's failure in the business, his failure could be because he was not competent enough and does not have the skills required for the business. He could have learnt about the business, but nowhere in the poem talks about him learning the business. The wife as a woman in such community must have lot of experience in pap making because she is a woman, and since kitchen and food occupation are supposed to be for women she must have been involved in this craft right from her childhood. But men are not meant for the kitchen as the society believes and they are not as experienced as the woman in the art of making pap paste. If men and women were raised equally and gender roles didn't exist this man might have not failed in the business like he did. The oracle fails to consider this and blames his gender for his failure. This issue of gender could have been the same if it were the woman that opted for occupations that the society believes it for men. The oracle could have blamed a woman's gender for her failure if she opted for occupation like hunting.

The issue of gender role here contributes to patriarchy, where women are tagged as unfit for certain occupation and men are demeaned for involving in certain occupations that are tagged feminine. This Ifa divination poem backs up this patriarchy belief and gives it a platform to stand on. Many women in Africa are denied of their dream career because of these gender roles and many men are ashamed of being involved in certain occupations because Ifa considered them women occupation.

Gender Categorization and Sex Markers in Ifa Divination Poetry

Connell (1978; 1995) argues that gender emerged as a result of perceptions imposed on the various reproductive organs of the human body. Perceptions, interpretations, and definitions femininities and masculinity champion are what impact upon human understanding and values placed on the body. Gender is the creation of human agency at both institutional and structural levels, which covertly constrained men and women. According to Connell (1995), there are three major structures gender relations are ordered and men and women activities are inhibited: labour, power and sexual emotions – these are constantly merged to evolve or create gender order, which is the gender structure that inform the hierarchical ordering or structure of gender relations in the society.

Kessler and McKenna (1978) suggest that, while assignment to a sex category occurs first at birth (or perhaps even prenatally), people continue to categorize one another as males or females throughout life. This process of attribution is the means through which gender distinctions emerge and are recreated. As Kessler and McKenna maintain, adults typically lack the kind of information about others' bodies that is used to assign sex category at birth. In "particular, since clothing usually hides people's genitals from the view of others, people rely on other markers to assign a sex category. These markers may include physical

characteristics, such as hair, body type, or voice, or they may include aspects of dress, mannerisms, or behaviour” (Kessler and McKenna 1978: p.165).

What count as markers of sex category, according to Wharton (2005), depends heavily on cultural circumstances and thus vary widely across time, place, and social group. By way of explanation, Wharton cites the American society and says that long hair on men became more common among some segments of American society during the 1960s than it had been previously. Accordingly, as sex markers change so are views about gender. This now questions the assumption whether facial characteristic are reliable markers of sex.

Furthermore, on the question of external sex makers, Kessler and McKenna (1978:1-2) observes that if we ask by what criteria a person might classify someone as being either male or female, the answers appear so self-evident as to make the question trivial. But consider a list of items that differentiate males from females. There are none that always and without exception are true of only one gender. No behavioural characteristic (e.g., crying or physical aggression) is always present or never present for one gender. Neither can physical characteristics – either visible (e.g., beards), unexposed (e.g., genitals), or normally unexamined (e.g., gonads) – always differentiate the genders.

This brings to mind the Odu, “Okoro-Meji,” which reads thus:

One Okanran here
One Okanran there
Okanran becomes two
It became droppings in the truth
Divined for breast when coming to earth
Breast was told to offer a sacrifice
Breast refused to offer the sacrifice
On the earth, Breast went to chest of men
Men climb trees and fight wars
Thus, breast found no rest
Breast consulted Ifa priests
It was divined that Breast should offer a sacrifice
Breast hearkened to the divination and offer the sacrifice
Breast now moved to the chest of women

Women do not climb trees nor fight wars
Breast found peace
Eventually, breast found honour and respect

Okanran kan nihin-in
Okanran kan l'ohun-un
Okanran di meji odo oduro l'ododo
A difa fun Omu nigba ti n lo isaluaye
Won ni ko'rubo
Ko korubo
O dele aye, o so si aya Okunrin
Okunrin a gun igi, won a lo jagun
Omu ko ni isinmi
O n wa ifokanbale
O gba oko awo lo
Babalawo ni ki o rubo
O gbo riru ebo o ru
Obinrin o ni igi gun, beni ko ni ogun ja
Ni omu ba ri ifokanbale
Nigbeyin, omu ri aponle ati iyi

Although the above Ifa divination poem is aetiological it however provides clues to understand gender category, sex designation and sex markers. One major thing that differentiates a woman and man is the fact that Women have breast and men have flat chest, women have vagina and men have penis. Between these sex-identifying maker in an adult human is the breast, because it is more conspicuous than the vagina that can be hidden in cloths but the breast is protruded. The breast is one unique attribute of women and can stand in as a synecdoche for women.

This poem presents a society of somewhat physical equality between men and women, where both men and women did not have breast, they are physically the same yet the society still makes provision for gender and gender roles. These two humans do not have breast yet the society still classifies them as weak, positions

them and manipulates them to into believing they are weak and are not meant for any work they choose. They are not meant to climb trees, fight wars because they are women even though they are same with men at this level. This shows that gender inequality is majorly not about physical status but about the fact that a particular gender just wants lead at all cost and sees themselves as superiors. When breast came to the earth (which represents weakness), the first person it came to meet was men, meaning it can relate with men- hence making him its first choice. However, the oracle, which upholds gender roles and gender stereotype, has to refer breast to women because women should not climb trees, women should not fight wars. The oracle is the custodian of the society gender values, and the value of gender inequality, gender roles and gender stereotype, hence he had to advice breast to move to women.

Breast found dignity and respect in staying with women because they are the subordinated gender. As breast found peace, dignity and honour with the women due to the fact women do not struggle for economic and political powers and freedom and do not go beyond their gender role. Women are conceived to be content, do not go beyond the position that society placed them; do not dream above the dreams the society recommends for it; so, does the woman also gains honour and respect by doing these things. Hence, once a woman starts going outside her gender role and aspire for more the breast becomes troubled and the losses honour, respect and peace just like the woman.

This Ifa divination poem attempts to curtain women through gender roles and promotes patriarchy in the Yoruba society. The fact that the women are expected to the weak ones, those meant for petty occupation, those that their riches can make a man jealous and have men ego bruised and it is never the other way round. From the fact that breast suits women better because she is the supposed weak one. This poem also shows how the society curtain women; with fake dignity and respect, the society seems to accord them for being in their gender roles and not wanting to aspire for more. The dignity the breast found in woman, which will definitely extend to women is the same dignity that a man would consider a shame. This means it was not really dignity as such; it was only a way of taming women and promoting patriarchy in the society.

Another aspect of the poem worthy of attention is the fact that breast which is a sex marker is first associated with men before it comes to women. Although the reason breast left men chest is attributed to their constant restlessness; it however denotes the fact that gender makers and configuration are not static, corroborating Connell (1978; 1995) and Matthews (1984) contentions that gender is a process; it is the reflection of human agencies of power relations, which is subject to changes emanating from resistance and acceptance. This means that gender configuration is not static, it moves with the times, and it is influenced by people's yearnings and

aspirations, and the socio-political and economic conditions of the time which are the agencies that create gender relations and order.

Conclusion

This paper reveals that Ifa divination poetry plays significant role in assigning gender to people. Starting with “Odu Ifa Okanran –Meji” where in the female gender is dispossessed economically due to the type of profession that is accorded the gender which is that of making pap paste. The paper reveals further that women are designated gender roles because society dominated by patriarchy does not want women to grow beyond their assigned position so that they may remain subjugated economically. As such, when women are able to negotiate their subjugated condition and make the best out of it, men desire to lay claim to them as seen in the case of Iwori and Onigoosun. The reason women are at the lower wrung of the economic and social ladders is because of the gender roles they are assigned, even though they work so hard and contribute to global economy, yet they constitute the highest index of poverty rate. Although Ifa divination poetry praises women as seen in Iwori’s success in pap paste making and Women and Breast, are symbolic undertones that denigrate women. Under the guise of admiration, Ifa divination poetry declasses women and make them subservient to patriarchy. The paper also reveals that gender roles and gender markers change with time and that gender schema and sexual dimorphism are not static, although these makers may be peculiar to one gender their distinction is not always clear-cut.

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